
Post-Independence West Bengal's Economic and Political Crisis and Utpal Dutta's Drama: A Brief Assessment

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ABSTRACT

After the independence and partition of Bengal in 1947 West Bengal was formed with 1/3 of Bengal. As a result most of the jut productive region and far tile land went into the part of West Pakistan. At the same time a terrible in flue of refugees from East Pakistan went on for a few decades. At the same time goes on the behavior of Central Government very like a step mother to West Bengal which drives the socio-economic condition of West Bengal to an unbearable condition. The impact of the West Bengal Government from the political background of West Bengal in a way based on which the play of "Borgi Elo Dese" by Utpal Dutta was performed, which also indicates again the crisis of the Centre-State relationship. Especially foreign influences in Indian economy, deception by Center in sanctioning finance in five year plans, discrimination in distributing capital investment and in raw material transformed West Bengal that is the hole of eastern region to be the colonies of the centre-all this things were represented by Mr.Dutta in his play

Introduction: In 1947 India's gaining the independence and consequently dissection at India represented West Bengal in such a reality that it was the Bengal without its fertile land. At the same time the parted state / Province had to put up with the influx of refugees as the by-product of the independence. Along with this acute behavior of the Centre to West Bengal like that of a step-mother that threw the economic-

social plight of W.B. to an unbearable condition whose impact also fell into the politics of W.B. ; especially , the agitations by the Communist Parties one after the other, gradual deception of the Central Government over-humanistic (based on humanism) efforts of Bidhan Roy, the total failure of the State Government builds the background of West Bengal in such a way that it lights on the deadlock of the Centre-State relationship in Utpal Dutta's Bargi Elo Deshe once again. Undoubtedly the then situation of West Bengal's political and economical state on which the play was composed and analyzed the situation of that time claimed specially to be referred to. In the contemporary documents of the communist parties we see the same type of matter. The then socio-economic and political situation, Centre-State relationship, criticism inside the communist parties has undoubtedly reflected in this drama. It was done in such a way which requires to be recapped of the politics and drama of that time.

Main Text: Shortly after the independence there takes place the influx of huge numbers of helpless uprooted refugees into West Bengal. The economy and society of Bengal was broken down badly by the influx of the huge number of these uprooted refugees. The exchange of population performed successfully in Punjab solved the problem of Punjab but the Centre's deception about rehabilitation and assistance in West Bengal thrust the lives of the refugees into an unbearable situation.

After the independence the Central Govt. introduces the mixed economy. It was said that in this model the state and Private firms, not only will co-ordinate one with another but also will be complementary to one another. (1) It was aimed to develop India's through 5-year-plans but India's economy couldn't work freely in spite of being free from the British imperialism; India became just a semi-colony out of a full colony of the British. "India became dependent on many other imperialist powers. (2) In the post-independence period time when other states of India were flourishing the capitalist production systems, around that time severe troubles were looming large on the economy of West Bengal. It was because the national industrial policy and continuous sucking the economy of West Bengal almost broke down at that time. (3)

The year 1959 in West Bengal was eventful. In that year food crisis reached the climax. Many essential commodities like rice were vanished from the open market and in many villages the situation loomed like a famine. There went angry resentment in farmers and labourers. They shouted demanding for food and began frequent mass movement angry protests, but, instead of considering the demands of the mass people with sympathy, the Congress Government took the way of ruthless suppression over the people. They wanted enough food for cheap price, but they got beaten like hell, tear gas, and bullet instead. It was said that 80 people died in the food movement in 1959(4). In 1967 a coalition government was

formed but it fell after nine months in November and in 1968 President's Rule was imposed upon West Bengal On February 20. In 1969 the Yukta Front Coalition government was formed for the second time on 25th of February which didn't last more than 13 months; this government faced a fall on 16th of March 1970.

The year of 167 has been remarkable for another reason in the History of West Bengal. Under the rebel the rebels of Maoists there took place a rebellion of farmers in Naksalbari of North Bengal. But the agitation died down.

Utpal Dutta represented skillfully using the jurisdiction court through simile of that period of time in 1972 in the background of Bargi Elo Deshe, especially foreign impact in Indian economic, deprivation of money sanction for West Bengal in Five Year Plans, investment in industries of and partial distribution of raw materials, turning West Bengal into a colony of the Centre, etc, which have skillfully been put up by Shree Dutta in his drama.

A boy of Naxalism of 17 years old, named Goutam was killed by the police. His parents and his brother who were party members of CPIM went to an advocate Mr. Haradhan Bagchi for investigation and justice of that murder. In the end a Judicial Investigation Committee was started under the advocate's endeavour to investigate Goutam Mukherji's death. The Royal witness Mr. G.C. Ghosh, a former IAS officer submitted his reports to jurisdiction that the law and order in Bengal had broken down badly from murders, injuring people, strikes, gheraos (confinements) in Bengal and capitalists were heaving Bengal, although the Central Government had been trying to keep up the economy through 5 year plans(5). Those were the reasons for which President's Rule had been imposed in the state. (6)

The complaints that Mr. Ghosh made were not true which had been proved by advocate Mr. Haradhan Banerjee with different pieces of information mentioned. He showed that the Central Government had been trapped in economic dependency pact by the imperialist countrie. He showed it from the report of the economic Committee of India Government that India was compelled to invest 2824.70 crore rupees in government industries within which American capital was 2034 crores. What came out of this capital investment as profit was going out abroad. (7) The India Government was also compelled to spend 2500 crore rupees to buy wheat from America and India Government took a loan of 3306 crores of rupees from the USA. (8) In 1947 there were 84 national-international joint venture companies in India, but in 1964 it increased up to 2015. (9) He also proved that there were influences of America in implementing 5-year plans. (10)

He picked out various kinds of information from India Government book of India 1969 to prove the lack of truth in information that many companies were leaving Bengal. (11) He showed that there were 9055 companies working on in Bengal where as in Maharastra there were 5546 companies. In his opinion there were other reasons behind the breakdown of Bengal's economy. According to the data of India Government-published Fourth Five-Year Plan what India achieved out of exporting tea of Assam and North Bengal, iron, mica of Bihar, jute of Bengal, steel of Bengal and Bihar, petroleum of Assam was more than half of the total exports but with the money out of Eastern India's exports, India Government imported machineries from abroad and established factories in other states. Fertilizers and yarn bought from outside where being supplied to, especially, in the states of Maharastra and Gujrat. In comparison to other states less money was sanctioned for West Bengal in the Fourth Five-Year Plan, (12) Thus the Eastern Region turned to the colony of the Centre. This way the resources from Bengal were carried outside and that's why Bengal's economy was breaking down. The Centre was in no way willing to let off the Eastern Region for it was a very good place for squeezing it dry; that's why President's Rule was imposed in Bengal. The costs of steel of Bihar and Bengal were cheaper than of other states but the Central Government forced to raise their prices. The Central Government t helped the coal mines of other states so as to keep their coal prices down while the coal of Bihar and Bengal would nobody buy. (13)

By the end of the drama we got to know that Goutam was the hindrance for sucking labourers; that's why the police killed him plan fully. Besides, the factory manager Gangapada's order Mihir Chakraborty was murdered to break up the union of the police constables, and Goutam was framed into it.

'Defeat the conspiracy of the Centre to make West Bengal the colony of the Centre was the slogan of the Communist Party of India (M). In the documentary of West Bengal State Committee 1972 it was said there were reasons for economic underdevelopment of West Bengal, '1947, August 15, when the nation was independent, West Bengal was on the top in economy, cultural and political sectors. The Congress Party being in power for 20 years at a stretch in the Centre and in all other states made West Bengal go broke (14)

In that documentary it was said about the tax squeezing that Central Government collected 217.81 crore rupees from West Bengal as excise duty in 1969-70 fiscal year, but from the collected tax it gave only 24.07 crore rupees. (15)

About the looting through jute exports the Communist Party of India had the same type of say 'India attained as foreign money from exports abroad out of which a big amount came through jute and jute-

products exports but with the foreign money attained by exporting things from jute industries, still West Bengal's claims were not met. (16)

In the internal discussion of Communist Party, it was said that the labourers' resentment was not responsible for close-down of factories, though the Congress men went on saying in the Anandabazar and the Jugantar that the workers' resentment was responsible for the factory shutdowns. Only a few days ago the governor of West Bengal said that 30% of the closed factories were closed down because of workers' agitation; not the other factories. (17)

For the reason about discrimination of investments the Communist Party had its say: 'Hundreds of engineering factories, 18 cotton mills were closed down. The reasons that the factories were closed down were the lack of order for production and for lack of raw material, and the other was the lack of capital. About that investment, too, the Congress Government of the Centre went to with the principle of acute discrimination to West Bengal. (18)

Usually a historian cannot write down history of the period of time they are living. So, the history Bengal after two decades of independence was written down a few decades. All the same Utpal Dutta, a thinker of politics and dramatist of that period of time was compelled to use simile in his drama which, certainly proved to be his deep sharp sights, political knowledge, and evaluation in the drama of Bargi Elo Deshe, which was in no way less important than historians' researches, or rather, it would be acceptable and appreciable as a unique bonanza of today's researches. The way the political documents and the incidents of those days were noticed in the drama was virtually a pathfinder to the present days' researchers.

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